

經濟部水利署水利規劃試驗所

112年「下一代淹水潛勢圖產製及模型建置」

教育訓練

計畫主持人 張哲豪 教授

2023/05/05

注意事項

- 線上課程
 - 顯示名稱 姓名_單位
- 線上簽到
 - 上午
 - 下午
- 討論區 (google chat)
 - 課程內容更新或問題回報
- 錯誤訊息回報方式
 - 討論區 (google chat)
 - Email

數位簽到資訊 (上午)

本會議採數位簽到，請於以下時間內完成簽到，感謝配合！

簽到時間：2023/05/05 8:00~12:00

*水利署同仁請持公務雲APP簽到

*非水利署同仁（或未安裝公務雲APP之署內同仁），請掃描開啟網頁簽到
<https://cloud.wra.gov.tw/assetBookingCheckIn.do?token=e3ea8d2dc2>

數位簽到資訊 (下午)

本會議採數位簽到，請於以下時間內完成簽到，感謝配合！

簽到時間：2023/05/05 12:00~16:00

*水利署同仁請持公務雲APP簽到

*非水利署同仁（或未安裝公務雲APP之署內同仁），請掃描開啟網頁簽到

<https://cloud.wra.gov.tw/assetBookingCheckIn.do?token=f18a4330ab>

討論區

- 使用google chat
- 課程內容更新或問題回報

- 原先報名不是使用google 帳號，再提供一組可以用的google 帳號或gmail

如何提供問題或錯誤訊息

截圖搭配 **Show Log**，複製錯誤訊息給我們使用email 或利用 討論區

The screenshot displays the DeltaShell software interface. The top menu bar includes 'File', 'Home', 'View', 'Tools', 'Map', 'Spatial Operations', 'Run All', 'Run Current', 'Run Script', 'Find', 'Open Manual', 'Start Screen', 'License', and 'About'. A 'Show Log' button is highlighted in the 'Tools' section. Below the menu bar, the 'Project' panel shows a project named '3826'. The main workspace displays a map with a blue overlay. A 'Messages' panel at the bottom shows a list of system messages, including 'Loaded project C:\Users\...', 'File C:\Users\...', 'Network has changed, clearing results.', 'Creating database session ...', 'Creation of configuration took 140 ms', 'Loading project C:\Users\...', 'Project closed', 'Closing current project ...', 'Hiding splash screen ...', 'Started in 5.34 sec', 'Project Project1 saved', and 'Waiting until new project is initialized ...'. A 'Show Log' dialog box is overlaid on the map, showing a list of log entries with timestamps and messages, such as 'DeltaShell.Gui.App.App_Startup - Starting Delta Shell ...' and 'DeltaShell.Core.DeltaShellApplication.Run - Initializing plugins ...'.

- ✓ 如有初步錯誤可以從下方**訊息/狀態列**獲得資訊。
- ✓ 若需要進一步的錯誤指定，可從上方 Home分頁的 **Show Log** 內，複製錯誤訊息即可

如何提供問題或錯誤訊息

截圖搭配 **Show Log**，複製錯誤訊息給我們使用email 或利用 討論區

操作狀態描述：匯入XXXX檔案、網格繪製、模擬....

問題說明：出現錯誤訊息、程式卡住不動、跳出重新啟動、程式自行關閉

畫面截圖：

Log 檔案：

練習專案作業(6/19前繳交)

- 鹽水溪排水
- 網格畫設24m+加密6m (2個重點區域)
 - 加密區域大於10公頃
- 包含溢堤線+建物區塊+觀測點
- 降雨量+潮位
- 檢查項目
 - 專案可執行
 - 觀測點模擬時間序列輸出(水深)
 - 淹水模擬成果輸出

基礎圖資與水文氣象資料預計於5/12前提供

112年 「下一代淹水潛勢圖產製及模型建置」

教育訓練

一二維物件匯入及建立

與

上下游邊界設定及模式執行

沈志全 博士

2023/05/05

完整課程名稱

教學內容

1 DFlow FM介紹及安裝

- 1-1 軟體簡介
- 1-2 軟體安裝與問題排除
- 1-3 介面操作

2 計算網格畫設

- 2-1 多邊形和線段劃設
- 2-2 規則網格畫設
- 2-3 局部加密功能

3 一二維物件匯入及建立

- 3-1 SOBEK匯入一維物件
- 3-2 DFlow建立一二維物件
- 3-3 一二維物件連接
- 3-4 建物區塊與溢堤線前處理

4 上下游邊界設定及模式執行

- 4-1 雨量及潮位設定
- 4-2 輸出內容與專案模擬

5 淹水模擬成果產製及內部展示功能

- 5-1 模式觀測點位成果輸出
- 5-2 模式成果與專案檔輸出
- 5-3 模式淹水深度剖面線觀看

4/28

課程項目	時間	時數	課程內容
報到	08:30 至 09:00	30 分鐘	人員報到
開場	09:00 至 09:05	5 分鐘	開場致詞 (主持人)
計畫說明	09:05 至 09:10	5 分鐘	訓練緣由與目的 (水利規劃試驗所)
最小模型建置	09:10 至 10:10	1 小時	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ 二維模式 ✓ 二維模式+一維模式+兩水下水道 講師：徐志宏 博士
DFlow FM 介紹 與 計算網格畫設	10:10 至 12:10 13:00 至 15:00	5 小時	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ 介面操作 ✓ 規則網格畫設 ✓ 局部加密功能 講師：沈志全博士
問題與討論	15:00 至 16:00	1 小時	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ 問題與討論 講師：張哲豪 教授、徐志宏博士、沈志全博士

5/5

課程項目	時間	時數	課程內容
報到	08:30 至 09:00	30 分鐘	人員報到
一二維物件匯入 及建立	09:00 至 12:00	3 小時	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ SOBEK 匯入一維物件 ✓ DFlow 建立一二維物件 ✓ 一二維物件連接 ✓ 建物區塊與溢堤線前處理 講師：沈志全博士
上下游邊界設定 及模式執行	13:00 至 15:00	2 小時	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ 雨量及潮位設定 ✓ 輸出內容與專案模擬 講師：沈志全博士
問題與討論	15:00 至 16:00	1 小時	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ 問題與討論 講師：張哲豪 教授、沈志全博士 徐志宏博士

5/19

課程項目	時間	時數	課程內容
報到	08:30 至 09:00	30 分鐘	人員報到
淹水模擬成果產製及 內部展示功能	09:00 至 12:00	3 小時	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ 模式觀測點位成果輸出 ✓ 模式專案成果輸出 講師： 沈志全博士
操作功能補充	13:00 至 15:00	2 小時	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ 資料前處理 ✓ 模式運算 ✓ 模式後處理 講師： 沈志全博士
問題與討論	15:00 至 16:00	1 小時	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ 問題與討論 講師： 張哲豪 教授、 沈志全博士

教育訓練課程目標

了解 Dflow FM 模式操作與模式建置步驟

- MESH 網格建立
- DEM 匯入
- MESH 網格高程內插
- 圖資操作
 - 資料匯入、放大、縮小、圖層調整
 - 坐標系統設定
- 水文氣象資料設定與匯入
- 物件新增與刪除
 - 建物區塊、溢堤線、監測點、抽水站、閘門、下水道、河道、斷面
- 模式模擬與檢視

課程共享資料夾清單與架構

名稱 ↑

 Course

教材、範例專案、時間序列資料

 raster

網格資料

 software

軟體

 vector

向量資料

• 本日使用檔案介紹與說明

... > Course > 20230505 ▾ 👤

名稱

📁	exercise_01_0505.zip	👤	練習案例與SOBEK專案
📄	rainfall.csv	👤	降雨量資料
📄	tide.csv	👤	潮位資料

• 本日使用檔案介紹與說明

Course\20230505\exercise_01_0505.zip

名稱	說明
sobek_input.dsproj_data	已匯入SOBEK專案(無網格)
sobek_input.dsproj	
TN_YS1.lit.7z	SOEBK 專案

TN_YS1.lit.7z 請解壓縮後 置放於20230505 資料夾內

SOEBK 專案 TN_YS1.lit

• 本日使用檔案介紹與說明

• 向量資料夾

... > vector > 20230505 ▾

名稱

溢堤線

建物區塊

監測檢視點

監測檢視點SHP(參考)

接續 4 月 28 日成果內容已 完成網格內插與加密格網

The screenshot displays the Delft3D FM Suite 2023.02 1D2D (2023.02) software interface. The main window shows a GIS map of a coastal area with a blue grid overlay. The interface includes a menu bar (File, Home, View, Tools, Map, Spatial Operations, Grid), a toolbar with various GIS tools, a Project tree on the left, a Properties panel, a Messages log at the bottom, and an Operations panel on the right.

Messages Log:

Icon	Message	Timestamp
Info	Running this model requires the OutputDirectory to be overwritten to: output	2023-04-26 13:52:12.744
Info	Project Project1 saved	2023-04-26 13:52:12.672
Warning	Creating database session ...	2023-04-26 13:52:12.294
Success	Creating database schema	2023-04-26 13:52:12.272

Coordinate system: "WGS 84 / Pseudo-Mercator" (EPSG: 3857) - Current map coordinates: 13385237.2973768, 2638116.69392281

接續 4 月 2 8 日內容

使用 Merge Operations

The screenshot displays the Delft3D FM Suite software interface. The main window shows a 2D model of a river or channel system, rendered in shades of blue and green, indicating different bed levels or depths. The interface includes a menu bar at the top with options like File, Home, View, Tools, and GIS. The 'Tools' menu is open, and the 'Merge Operations' tool is highlighted with a red box and a circled '2'. The 'Operations' panel on the right side of the interface shows a tree view of the model's components, with 'Bed Level' and 'Interpolate 1' highlighted by a red box and a circled '1'. The 'Messages' panel at the bottom left shows a list of system messages, including 'Updated spatial operations of coverage Bed Level with changed grid.' and 'Running this model requires the OutputDirectory to be overwritten to: output.'

Project1 - Delft3D FM Suite 2022.04 1D2D (2022.04)

File Home View Tools GIS Config DIMR

Layer Bed Level

Legend

Decor... Edit

Project FM_model X

Project1

- FM_model
 - General
 - 1D
 - 2D
 - Area
 - Grid
 - Bed Level
 - Initial Conditions
 - Boundary Condition
 - Physical Parameters
 - Sources and Sinks
 - 1D2D Links
 - Output

Operations

- Bed Level
 - Bed Level
 - set 1
 - Interpolate 1
 - set 2
 - Interpolate 2

Messages

- Updated spatial operations of coverage Bed Level with changed grid. 2023-05-03 20:35:45.619
- Running this model requires the OutputDirectory to be overwritten to: output. 2023-05-03 20:33:13.515
- Project Project1 saved 2023-05-03 20:33:13.290
- Creating database session ... 2023-05-03 20:33:12.790
- Creating database schema ... 2023-05-03 20:33:12.749

Messages Time Navigator

Chart Regi... Map Ope... Tool...

接續 4 月 2 8 內容

使用 Merge Operations

The screenshot displays the Delft3D FM Suite software interface. The main window shows a map view of a river network with a grid overlay. The 'Merge Operations' tool is highlighted in the top toolbar. A red box highlights the 'Operations' panel on the right, which is currently empty, with the text 'Merge完成' (Merge Complete) written below it. A red circle with the number '3' is in the top right corner of the map view.

Project1 - Delft3D FM Suite 2022.04 1D2D (2022.04)

File Home View Tools Map Spatial Operations Grid Config DIMR

Layer Bed Level Polygon Line Points Merge Operations Import Set Value Interpolate Copy to samples Copy to spatial data Add rasterfile samples Crop Contour Smoothing Delete Gradient Overwrite Value Merge spatial data

Project1 FM_model x

Project1

- FM_model
 - General
 - 1D
 - 2D
 - Area
 - Grid
 - Bed Level
 - Initial Conditions
 - Boundary Condition
 - Physical Parameters
 - Sources and Sinks
 - 1D2D Links
 - Output

Operations

Refresh

Merge完成

Messages

- Updated spatial operations of coverage Bed Level with changed grid. 2023-05-03 20:35:45.619
- Running this model requires the OutputDirectory to be overwritten to: output 2023-05-03 20:33:13.515
- Project Project1 saved 2023-05-03 20:33:13.290
- Creating database session ... 2023-05-03 20:33:12.790
- Creating database schema ... 2023-05-03 20:33:12.749

Chart Regi... Map Ope... Tool...

匯入SOBEK物件

使用SOEBK 專案 TN_YS1.lit

The screenshot displays the Delft3D FM Suite 2022.04 1D2D (2022.04) interface. The Project tree on the left shows a project named 'Project1' containing a model named 'FM_model'. A right-click context menu is open over 'FM_model', with the 'Import...' option highlighted by a red box and labeled with a circled '2'. A red arrow labeled with a circled '1' points to the 'FM_model' in the tree. The main map area shows a geographical map of a coastal region with a large blue-shaded area representing the model domain. The Messages panel at the bottom shows several status messages, including 'Updated spatial operations of coverage Bed Level with changed grid.', 'Running this model requires the OutputDirectory to be overwritten to: output', 'Project Project1 saved', 'Creating database session ...', and 'Creating database schema ...'. The Time Navigator at the bottom left shows 'Messages' and 'Time Navigator' tabs.

匯入SOBEK物件

使用SOEBK 專案 TN_YS1.lit

匯入SOBEK物件

使用SOEBK 專案 TN_YS1.lit

匯入SOBEK物件

使用SOEBK 專案 TN_YS1.lit

SOBEK WaterFlow FM importer

Select file

<< TN_YS1.lit > TN_YS1.lit

組合管理 新增資料夾

名稱	修改日期	類型
3	2023/5/1 下午 04:10	檔案資料夾
CMTWORK	2023/5/1 下午 04:18	檔案資料夾
FIXED	2023/5/1 下午 06:13	檔案資料夾
NEWSTART	2023/5/1 下午 04:08	檔案資料夾
SOBEK	2023/5/1 下午 04:10	檔案資料夾
CASELIST.CMT	2023/5/1 下午 04:10	CMT 檔案

檔案名稱(N): CASELIST.CMT

All supported files (networkt...

開啟(O) 取消

檔案選擇 CASELIST.CMT

Messages

- Updated spatial operations of coverage Bed Level with changed grid.
- Running this model requires the OutputDirectory to be overwritten to: output
- Project Project1 saved
- Creating database session ...
- Creating database schema ...

匯入SOBEK物件

使用SOEBK 專案 TN_YS1.lit

SOBEK WaterFlow FM importer

Select SOBEK case or network file

Filename: C:\WRAP2023\Course\20230505\exercise_01_0505\TN_YS1 lit\TN_YS1 lit\CASELIST.CMT

Select a case:

- 3 for Delft3d1d2d

< Previous **Next >** Cancel

Messages

- Updated spatial operations of coverage Bed Level with changed grid. 2023-05-03 20:35:45.619
- Running this model requires the OutputDirectory to be overwritten to: output 2023-05-03 20:33:13.515
- Project Project1 saved 2023-05-03 20:33:13.290
- Creating database session ... 2023-05-03 20:33:12.790
- Creating database schema ... 2023-05-03 20:33:12.749

匯入SOBEK物件

使用SOEBK 專案 TN_YS1.lit

SOBEK WaterFlow FM importer

Select parts to import
Use the checkboxes to select

Select all

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Branches and nodes	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Cross-sections
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Structures (weirs, bridges etc.)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Lateral sources
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Measurement stations (observation points)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Friction (roughness)
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Initial Conditions	<input type="checkbox"/> Boundary conditions (data)
<input type="checkbox"/> Lateral sources data	<input type="checkbox"/> Grid points (computational grid)
<input type="checkbox"/> Retentions	<input type="checkbox"/> Model and case settings

取消勾選下方五個選項

10

11

< Previous **Finish** Cancel

Messages

Updated spatial operations of coverage Bed Level with changed grid.	2023-05-03 20:35:45.619
Running this model requires the OutputDirectory to be overwritten to: output	2023-05-03 20:33:13.515
Project Project1 saved	2023-05-03 20:33:13.290
Creating database session ...	2023-05-03 20:33:12.790
Creating database schema ...	2023-05-03 20:33:12.749

Messages Time Navigator

Chart Regi... Map Ope... Tool...

SOBEK匯入完成

使用SOEBK 專案 TN_YS1.lit

SOBEK匯入完成

匯入完成，取消勾選 **Bed Level** 圖層 以便觀察

The screenshot displays the Delft3D FM Suite software interface. The main map shows a coastal area with a blue water body and a red coastline. A red arrow points to the 'Bed Level' checkbox in the layer legend, which is highlighted with a red box. The software interface includes a menu bar (File, Home, View, Tools, Map, Spatial Operations, Grid, Config, DIMR), a toolbar with various GIS tools, a project tree on the left, and a messages window at the bottom. The messages window contains the following text:

Messages

- While importing initial conditions we encountered the following 2 warnings:
- Could not import channel initial conditions for branch 553, it is not of type Channel. Skipping import of this initial condition. 2023-05-03 20:37:38.123
- Friction data for the following cross-section definitions have not been found. The main bed of branch is used as roughness data. Definition "P01_D75600-0259", cross-section "YS_D75600-0000", branch "YS_504" 2023-05-03 20:37:36.912
- Friction BDFR is linked to branch that does not exist; ignored. 2023-05-03 20:37:36.604
- 470_branch.470

SOBEK匯入完成

取消勾選 **Bed Level** 圖層 以便觀察

Project1 - Delft3D FM Suite 2022.04 1D2D (2022.04)

Layer: Bed Level

GIS: Spatial Operations, Grid, Config, DIMR

Tools: Polygon, Line, Points, Merge Operations, Import, Set Value, Interpolate, Copy to samples, Copy to spatial data, Add rasterfile samples, Merge spatial data, Crop, Contour, Smoothing, Delete, Gradient, Overwrite Value

Project: Project1

- FM_model
 - General
 - 1D
 - 2D
 - Area
 - Grid
 - Bed Level
 - Initial Conditions
 - Boundary Condition
 - Physical Parameters
 - Sources and Sinks
 - 1D/2D Links
 - Output

Map

- Map
 - FM_model
 - 1D
 - 2D
 - Area
 - Unstructured Grid
 - Bed Level
 - Initial Water Level
 - Boundary Conditions
 - Boundaries
 - Roughness
 - Viscosity
 - Diffusivity
 - Infiltration
 - Sources and Sinks
 - 1D/2D Links
 - Estimated Grid-snapped
 - Open Street Map

Messages

- While importing initial conditions we encountered the following 2 warnings:
 - Could not import channel initial conditions for branch 553, it is not of type Channel. Skipping import of this initial condition. 2023-05-03 20:37:38.123
 - Friction data for the following cross-section definitions have not been found. The main bed of branch is used as roughness data. Definition "P01_D75600-0259", cross-section "YS_D75600-0000", branch "YS_504" 2023-05-03 20:37:36.912
- Friction BDFR is linked to branch that does not exist; ignored. 2023-05-03 20:37:36.604
- 470_branch.470

調整計算節點

選擇select功能 (白色箭頭)

框選網格與SOBEK物件

Messages

While importing initial conditions we encountered the following 2 warnings:	2023-05-03 20:37:38.123
Could not import channel initial conditions for branch 553, it is not of type Channel. Skipping import of this initial condition.	
Friction data for the following cross-section definitions have not been found. The main bed of branch is used as roughness data. Definition "P01_D75600-0259", cross-section "YS_D75600-0000", branch "YS_504"	2023-05-03 20:37:36.912
Friction BDFR is linked to branch that does not exist; ignored. 470_branch.470	2023-05-03 20:37:36.604

調整計算節點

Remove computational grid nodes

The screenshot displays the Delft3D FM Suite 2022.04 1D2D (2022.04) interface. The main map shows a river network with a dense grid of blue and red nodes. A right-click context menu is open over the grid, with the option "Remove computational grid nodes" highlighted in red. A red circle with the number "3" is placed over the right-click action, and another red circle with the number "4" is placed over the highlighted menu option. The "Messages" panel at the bottom left shows several warning messages related to initial conditions and friction data. The "Map" panel on the right shows the current map configuration, including "FM_model", "1D", "2D", "Area", "Bed Level", "Boundary Conditions", "Sources and Sinks", and "1D/2D Links".

GIS Config DIMR

Project1 - Delft3D FM Suite 2022.04 1D2D (2022.04)

File Home View Tools Map Spatial Operations Grid Config DIMR

Generate links Add link Legend Scale Bar

North Arrow Zoom Previous Map Coordinate System Show Profile Add ditch layers

Zoom Next Export As Image Query Features Query Time Series

Edit Grid Profile Backgrou... Network Area Region Network Coverage

FM Region 1D2D Links Decorations Tools

Project FM_model X

Project1 FM_model General 1D 2D Area Grid Bed Level Initial Conditions Boundary Condition Physical Parameters Sources and Sinks 1D2D Links Output

Map Use focused layer

FM_model 1D 2D Area Unstructured Grid Bed Level Initial Water Level Boundary Conditions Boundaries Roughness Viscosity Diffusivity Infiltration Sources and Sinks 1D/2D Links Estimated Grid-snapped Open Street Map

Messages

While importing initial conditions we encountered the following 2 warnings:

Could not import channel initial conditions for branch 553, it is not of type Channel. Skipping import of this initial condition.

Friction data for the following cross-section definitions have not been found. The main bed of branch is used as roughness data. Definition "P01_D75600-0259", cross-section "YS_D75600-0000", branch "YS_504"

Friction BDFR is linked to branch that does not exist; ignored.

470_branch.470

Remove computational grid nodes

2023-05-03 20:37:36.912

2023-05-03 20:37:36.604

Chart Regi... Map Ope... Tool...

調整計算節點

Project1 - Delft3D FM Suite 2022.04 1D2D (2022.04)

選擇select功能 (白色箭頭)

框選網格與SOBEK物件

Messages

While importing initial conditions we encountered the following 2 warnings:	2023-05-03 20:37:38.123
Could not import channel initial conditions for branch 553, it is not of type Channel. Skipping import of this initial condition.	
Friction data for the following cross-section definitions have not been found. The main bed of branch is used as roughness data. Definition "P01_D75600-0259", cross-section "YS_D75600-0000", branch "YS_504"	2023-05-03 20:37:36.912
Friction BDFR is linked to branch that does not exist; ignored. 470_branch.470	2023-05-03 20:37:36.604

調整計算節點

Generate computational grid nodes in selected branch(es)

The screenshot displays the Delft3D FM Suite 2022.04 1D2D (2022.04) interface. The main window shows a map of a river network with a selected branch highlighted in blue. A context menu is open over this branch, and the option "Generate computational grid nodes in selected branch(es)" is highlighted with a red box. Red text annotations include "點擊右鍵" (Right-click) near the context menu and "新增計算節點" (Add computational nodes) near the highlighted option. The interface also shows a project tree on the left, a messages panel at the bottom, and various toolbars and panels.

Messages:

- While importing initial conditions we encountered the following 2 warnings:
- Could not import channel initial conditions for branch 553, it is not of type Channel. Skipping import of this initial condition.
- Friction data for the following cross-section definitions have not been found. The main bed of branch is used as roughness data.
Definition "P01_D75600-0259", cross-section "YS_D75600-0000", branch "YS_504"
- Friction BDFR is linked to branch that does not exist; ignored.
470_branch.470

調整計算節點

Project1 - Delft3D FM Suite 2022.04 1D2D (2022.04)

Generate Computational Grid

Create segments for:

- All branches
- Selected branches

If branch already has grid points:

- Generate new grid points
- Use existing grid points

Positions:

- None (Remove grid from branch)
- Preferred length: 50 m. 填入 50 m

Special locations:

- Cross Section
- Lateral Sources
- Structure: 10 m. in front and behind
- Minimum cell length: 0.5 m.

Messages

- While importing initial conditions we encountered the following 2 warnings:
- Could not import channel initial conditions for branch 553, it is not of type Channel. Skipping import of this initial condition. 2023-05-03 20:37:38.123
- Friction data for the following cross-section definitions have not been found. The main bed of branch is used as roughness data. Definition "P01_D75600-0259", cross-section "YS_D75600-0000", branch "YS_504" 2023-05-03 20:37:36.912
- Friction BDFR is linked to branch that does not exist; ignored. 2023-05-03 20:37:36.604
- 470_branch.470

建立1D2D連結

使用 **Generate links**

Project1 - Delft3D FM Suite 2022.04 1D2D (2022.04)

File View Tools Map GIS Spatial Operations Grid Config DIMR

Generate links

North Arrow Legend Scale Bar

Zoom Previous Map Coordinate System Show Profile

Zoom Next Export As Image

Query Features Query Time Series

Add ditch layers

Show Profile

Link Coverage Computational 1D Grid Add Route Show Side View

Project FM_model

Project1

FM_model

General

1D

2D

Area

Grid

Bed Level

Initial Conditions

Boundary Condition

Physical Parameters

Sources and Sinks

1D2D Links

Output

Map

Use focused layer

FM_model

1D

2D

Area

Unstructured Grid

Bed Level

Initial Water Level

Boundary Conditions

Boundaries

Roughness

Viscosity

Diffusivity

Infiltration

Sources and Sinks

1D/2D Links

Estimated Grid-snapped

Open Street Map

temp_layer

Messages

While importing initial conditions we encountered the following 2 warnings:

Could not import channel initial conditions for branch 553, it is not of type Channel. Skipping import of this initial condition.

Friction data for the following cross-section definitions have not been found. The main bed of branch is used as roughness data.

Definition "P01_D75600-0259", cross-section "YS_D75600-0000", branch "YS_504"

Friction BDFR is linked to branch that does not exist; ignored.

470_branch.470

2023-05-03 20:37:38.123

2023-05-03 20:37:36.912

2023-05-03 20:37:36.604

Messages Time Navigator

Chart Regi... Map Ope... Tool...

建立1D2D連結

連結成功

設定上下游邊界條件

進入 **General** 中的 **Time Frame** 調整時間

The screenshot displays the Delft3D FM Suite software interface. The main window is titled "Project1 - Delft3D FM Suite 2022.04 1D2D (2022.04)". The "General" tab is selected, and the "Time Frame" sub-tab is active. The "Time Frame" settings are highlighted with a red box, and the "Time step analysis" sub-tab is also visible. The "Time Frame" settings include:

- Max Courant nr: 0.7
- Reference date: 2021-07-30 00:00:00
- Time zone: 0
- User time step: 0 d 01: 00: 00.000
- Max. time step (s): 3600
- Initial time step (s): 3600
- Update interval for time dep roughness (s): 86400
- Start Time: 2021-07-30 18:00:00
- Stop Time: 2021-08-01 17:00:00

The "Time step analysis" sub-tab includes:

- Autotimestep exclude structure links:
- Exclude negative qin:

Annotations in the image include:

- A red box labeled "1" around the "General" tab in the Project tree.
- A red box labeled "2" around the "Time Frame" sub-tab.
- Red text "連續點選 General" (Click continuously General) next to the "General" tab.
- Red text "修改框選內容" (Modify selected content) below the "Time Frame" settings.

The Messages panel at the bottom shows several warnings:

- While importing initial conditions we encountered the following 2 warnings:
- Could not import channel initial conditions for branch 553, it is not of type Channel. Skipping import of this initial condition. (2023-05-03 20:37:38.123)
- Friction data for the following cross-section definitions have not been found. The main bed of branch is used as roughness data. Definition "P01_D75600-0259", cross-section "YS_D75600-0000", branch "YS_504" (2023-05-03 20:37:36.912)
- Friction BDFR is linked to branch that does not exist; ignored. (2023-05-03 20:37:36.604)

設定上下游邊界條件

進入 **General** 中的 **Output Parameters** 調整時間

3

修改框選內容 (同前頁 1 hr)

Messages

Icon	Message	Time
Warning	While importing initial conditions we encountered the following 2 warnings: Could not import channel initial conditions for branch 553, it is not of type Channel. Skipping import of this initial condition.	2023-05-03 20:37:38.123
Warning	Friction data for the following cross-section definitions have not been found. The main bed of branch is used as roughness data. Definition "P01_D75600-0259", cross-section "YS_D75600-0000", branch "YS_504"	2023-05-03 20:37:36.912
Warning	Friction BDFR is linked to branch that does not exist; ignored. 470_branch.470	2023-05-03 20:37:36.604

設定上下游邊界條件

匯入上游雨量

Project1 - Delft3D FM Suite 2022.04 1D2D (2022.04)

File Home View Tools

Clipboard Add Run Run Current Run Script Edit... Open Manual Start Screen License Show Log About Help

Project FM_model Meteo Editor X

Project1
FM_model
General
1D
2D
Area
Grid
Bed Level
Initial Conditions
Boundary Condition
Physical Parameters
Roughness
Viscosity
Diffusivity
Infiltration
Meteo items

①

② Add... Remove

③

④ OK Cancel

Messages

Icon	Message	Time
!	While importing initial conditions we encountered the following 2 warnings: Could not import channel initial conditions for branch 553, it is not of type Channel. Skipping import of this initial condition.	2023-05-03 20:37:38.123
!	Friction data for the following cross-section definitions have not been found. The main bed of branch is used as roughness data. Definition "P01_D75600-0259", cross-section "YS_D75600-0000", branch "YS_504"	2023-05-03 20:37:36.912
!	Friction BDFR is linked to branch that does not exist; ignored. 470_branch.470	2023-05-03 20:37:36.604

Chart Regi... Map Ope... Tool...

連續點選

Meteo items

設定上下游邊界條件

匯入上游雨量

The screenshot displays the Delft3D FM Suite 2022.04 1D2D (2022.04) interface. The main window shows a project tree on the left with 'FM_model' selected. The 'Precipitation rainfall (Global)' tab is active, showing a table with columns for 'Time [yyyy/MM/dd HH:mm:ss]' and 'Precipitation [mm day-1]'. A 'Generate' button is highlighted with a red box and a circled '5'. A 'Generate time series...' dialog box is open in the center, with the 'Generate new' radio button selected. The 'Time range' section shows 'Start' as 2021/ 7/30 下午 06:00:00 and 'End' as 2021/ 8/ 1 下午 05:00:00. The 'Timestep' is set to 1 day. The 'OK' button is highlighted with a red box and a circled '7'. A circled '6' is also present near the dialog box. The bottom of the interface shows a 'Messages' panel with several warning messages.

Project1 - Delft3D FM Suite 2022.04 1D2D (2022.04)

File Home View Tools Charting Chart

Clipboard Add Run All Run Current Run Script Find Open Manual Start Screen Show Log License About

Project FM_model Meteo Editor X

Clipboard import Csv import Csv export Generate

Time [yyyy/MM/dd HH:mm:ss] Precipitation [mm day-1]

Generate time series...

Generate new
Modify existing

Time range

Start 2021/ 7/30 下午 06:00:00

End 2021/ 8/ 1 下午 05:00:00

Timestep 0 1 0 0
days hours min sec

OK Cancel

Record 0 of 0 (1899-12-30)

Messages

- While importing initial conditions we encountered the following 2 warnings:
- Could not import channel initial conditions for branch 553, it is not of type Channel. Skipping import of this initial condition. 2023-05-03 20:37:38.123
- Friction data for the following cross-section definitions have not been found. The main bed of branch is used as roughness data. Definition "P01_D75600-0259", cross-section "YS_D75600-0000", branch "YS_504" 2023-05-03 20:37:36.912
- Friction BDFR is linked to branch that does not exist; ignored. 470_branch.470 2023-05-03 20:37:36.604

Chart Regi... Map Ope... Tool...

設定上下游邊界條件

匯入上游雨量

The screenshot displays the Delft3D FM Suite software interface. The 'Csv import' dialog box is open, showing a table of precipitation data. The table has two columns: 'Time [yyyy/MM/dd HH:mm:ss]' and 'Precipitation [mm day-1]'. The data shows a constant precipitation of 0 mm day-1 from 2021/07/30 18:00:00 to 2021/08/01 03:00:00. A red circle with the number '8' is placed over the 'Csv import' button. The background shows the 'Meteo Editor' window with a map and a legend for 'Precipitation [mm day-1]'. The 'Messages' panel at the bottom displays several warnings related to initial conditions and friction data.

Time [yyyy/MM/dd HH:mm:ss]	Precipitation [mm day-1]
2021/07/30 18:00:00	0
2021/07/30 19:00:00	0
2021/07/30 20:00:00	0
2021/07/30 21:00:00	0
2021/07/30 22:00:00	0
2021/07/30 23:00:00	0
2021/07/31 00:00:00	0
2021/07/31 01:00:00	0
2021/07/31 02:00:00	0
2021/07/31 03:00:00	0
2021/07/31 04:00:00	0
2021/07/31 05:00:00	0
2021/07/31 06:00:00	0
2021/07/31 07:00:00	0
2021/07/31 08:00:00	0
2021/07/31 09:00:00	0
2021/07/31 10:00:00	0
2021/07/31 11:00:00	0
2021/07/31 12:00:00	0
2021/07/31 13:00:00	0
2021/07/31 14:00:00	0
2021/07/31 15:00:00	0
2021/07/31 16:00:00	0
2021/07/31 17:00:00	0
2021/07/31 18:00:00	0
2021/07/31 19:00:00	0
2021/07/31 20:00:00	0
2021/07/31 21:00:00	0
2021/07/31 22:00:00	0
2021/07/31 23:00:00	0
2021/08/01 00:00:00	0
2021/08/01 01:00:00	0
2021/08/01 02:00:00	0
2021/08/01 03:00:00	0

Messages

- While importing initial conditions we encountered the following 2 warnings:
Could not import channel initial conditions for branch 553, it is not of type Channel. Skipping import of this initial condition. 2023-05-03 20:37:38.123
- Friction data for the following cross-section definitions have not been found. The main bed of branch is used as roughness data.
Definition "P01_D75600-0259", cross-section "YS_D75600-0000", branch "YS_504" 2023-05-03 20:37:36.912
- Friction BDFR is linked to branch that does not exist; ignored.
A7D_branch.A7D 2023-05-03 20:37:36.604

設定上下游邊界條件

匯入上游雨量

Welcome to the wizard

This wizard will allow you to import CSV data

9

Select CSV file
Select the CSV-file containing the data

Filename

10

選擇檔案

Select file

組合管理 新增資料夾

名稱	修改日期	類型
exercise_01_0505	2023/5/3 下午 08:27	檔案資料夾
rainfall.csv	2023/5/1 下午 11:57	Microsoft Excel ...
tide.csv	2023/5/1 下午 11:57	Microsoft Excel ...

11

選擇 rainfall.csv

檔案名稱(N): rainfall.csv

12

開啟(O) 取消

< Previous Next > Cancel

設定上下游邊界條件

匯入上游雨量

Select CSV file
Select the CSV-file containing the data

Filename: ...

13

< Previous **Next >** Cancel

Parse columns
Please indicate how the data should be parsed into columns

Delimiters:
 Tab Semicolon Use first row as header
 Space Comma Ignore empty lines

Data preview

time	mm/hr	mm/day
2021/7/30 18:00	0	0
2021/7/30 19:00	0	0
2021/7/30 20:00	0	0
2021/7/30 21:00	1.34	32.16
2021/7/30 22:00	0.58	13.92
2021/7/30 23:00	0	0
2021/7/31 00:00	0.13	3.12
2021/7/31 01:00	0.6	14.4
2021/7/31 02:00	3.76	90.24

14

< Previous **Next >** Cancel

設定上下游邊界條件

匯入上游雨量

Value parsing and column mapping
Please indicate how the values should be parsed and which columns should be used.

Culture info

Date time format:

Number format:

Column selection

Time: (15)

Precipitation: (16)

Filtering

Use filter Filter value:

Input preview

	time	mm/hr	mm/day
▶	2021/7/30 18:00	0	0
	2021/7/30 19:00	0	0
	2021/7/30 20:00	0	0
	2021/7/30 21:00	1.34	32.16
	2021/7/30 22:00	0.58	13.92
	2021/7/30 23:00	0	0

Result preview

	Time	Precipitation
▶	2021-07-30 18:00:00.000	0
	2021-07-30 19:00:00.000	0
	2021-07-30 20:00:00.000	0
	2021-07-30 21:00:00.000	32.16
	2021-07-30 22:00:00.000	13.92
	2021-07-30 23:00:00.000	0
	2021-07-31	3.12

(16)

Finish wizard

Press Finish to close the wizard.

(17)

設定上下游邊界條件

雨量匯入完成

The screenshot displays the Delft3D FM Suite interface. The main window shows a table of precipitation data imported from a global file. The table has two columns: 'Time [yyyy/MM/dd HH:mm:ss]' and 'Precipitation [mm day-1]'. The data spans from 2021/07/30 18:00:00 to 2021/08/01 03:00:00. A bar chart on the right visualizes this data, with the y-axis representing precipitation in mm day-1 (0 to 700) and the x-axis representing time. The chart shows several peaks, with the highest peak reaching approximately 700 mm day-1 on 2021/08/01 00:00:00. The interface also includes a project tree on the left, a messages panel at the bottom, and a map on the right.

Time [yyyy/MM/dd HH:mm:ss]	Precipitation [mm day-1]
2021/07/30 18:00:00	0
2021/07/30 19:00:00	0
2021/07/30 20:00:00	0
2021/07/30 21:00:00	32.16
2021/07/30 22:00:00	13.92
2021/07/30 23:00:00	0
2021/07/31 00:00:00	3.12
2021/07/31 01:00:00	14.4
2021/07/31 02:00:00	90.24
2021/07/31 03:00:00	68.4
2021/07/31 04:00:00	55.68
2021/07/31 05:00:00	371.28
2021/07/31 06:00:00	337.2
2021/07/31 07:00:00	53.04
2021/07/31 08:00:00	16.32
2021/07/31 09:00:00	198.24
2021/07/31 10:00:00	563.52
2021/07/31 11:00:00	179.04
2021/07/31 12:00:00	74.4
2021/07/31 13:00:00	84.48
2021/07/31 14:00:00	324
2021/07/31 15:00:00	195.6
2021/07/31 16:00:00	60.48
2021/07/31 17:00:00	24.96
2021/07/31 18:00:00	5.04
2021/07/31 19:00:00	7.92
2021/07/31 20:00:00	30
2021/07/31 21:00:00	219.84
2021/07/31 22:00:00	118.08
2021/07/31 23:00:00	75.6
2021/08/01 00:00:00	180
2021/08/01 01:00:00	288.48
2021/08/01 02:00:00	176.64
2021/08/01 03:00:00	111.12

設定上下游邊界條件

匯入下游潮位

The screenshot displays the Delft3D FM Suite 2022.04 1D2D (2022.04) interface. The main map shows a coastal region with a red boundary and a blue box highlighting a specific area. A red circle with the number '1' is placed over the blue box. The interface includes a menu bar (File, Home, View, Tools, Map, GIS), a toolbar with various GIS tools, and a project tree on the left. The project tree shows the following structure:

- Project1
 - FM_model
 - General
 - 1D
 - 2D
 - Area
 - Grid
 - Bed Level
 - Initial Conditions
 - Boundary Condition
 - Physical Parameters
 - Roughness
 - Viscosity
 - Diffusivity
 - Infiltration
 - Meteo items
 - Precipitation
 - Wind
 - Sources and Sinks
 - 1D2D Links
 - Output

The right-hand side of the interface shows a legend for the map, with the following items checked:

- FM_model
 - 1D
 - 2D
 - Area
 - Unstructured Grid
 - Bed Level
 - Initial Water Level
 - Boundary Conditions
 - Boundaries
 - Roughness
 - Viscosity
 - Diffusivity
 - Sources and Sinks
 - 1D/2D Links
 - Estimated Grid-snapped
- Open Street Map

The bottom of the interface shows a Messages panel with the following content:

Icon	Message	Time
Info	While importing initial conditions we encountered the following 2 warnings:	2023-05-03 20:37:38.123
Warning	Could not import channel initial conditions for branch 553, it is not of type Channel. Skipping import of this initial condition.	
Warning	Friction data for the following cross-section definitions have not been found. The main bed of branch is used as roughness data. Definition "P01_D75600-0259", cross-section "YS_D75600-0000", branch "YS_504"	2023-05-03 20:37:36.912
Error	Friction BDFR is linked to branch that does not exist; ignored. 470_branch.470	2023-05-03 20:37:36.604

用放大鏡顯示下游潮位區域

設定上下游邊界條件

匯入下游潮位

The screenshot displays the Delft3D FM Suite software interface. The main window shows a map of a river system with various features like '海墘一般管制區', '四草里', '安南區', '四草大橋', and '安南區'. A context menu is open over a node labeled 'YS_413 (Nodes)'. The menu options include 'Edit', 'Query time series', 'Remove Node', 'Export map as image', 'Generate computational grid nodes', 'Generate embankments', 'Remove computational grid nodes', 'Zoom to extents', and 'Import cross section(s) from csv'. The 'Edit' option is selected, and a sub-menu is visible with '- From selection' and 'YS_413 (Nodes)'. The 'Messages' panel at the bottom shows several warnings related to initial conditions and friction data.

點選河道下游節點，並右鍵開啟選單，進行編輯

設定上下游邊界條件

匯入下游潮位

The screenshot displays the Delft3D FM Suite software interface. The main window is titled "Project1 - Delft3D FM Suite 2022.04 1D2D (2022.04)". The interface includes a menu bar (File, Home, View, Tools), a toolbar with various icons, and a project tree on the left. The "Flow Data" panel is open, showing a list of data types. The item "H(t) : Water level time series" is highlighted with a red circle and a red box, indicating it is the selected option. Below the "Flow Data" panel, the "Messages" panel shows several warning messages related to initial conditions and friction data.

Flow Data

Type	Value
None	None
None	None
H(t)	Water level time series
Q(t)	Flow time series
Q(h)	Flow water level table
Q	Constant flow
H	Constant water level

Messages

Icon	Message	Time
Warning	While importing initial conditions we encountered the following 2 warnings:	2023-05-03 20:37:38.123
Warning	Could not import channel initial conditions for branch 553, it is not of type Channel. Skipping import of this initial condition.	
Warning	Friction data for the following cross-section definitions have not been found. The main bed of branch is used as roughness data.	2023-05-03 20:37:36.912
Warning	Definition "P01_D75600-0259", cross-section "YS_D75600-0000", branch "YS_504"	
Warning	Friction BDFR is linked to branch that does not exist; ignored.	2023-05-03 20:37:36.604
Warning	470_branch.470	

設定上下游邊界條件

匯入下游潮位

The screenshot displays the Delft3D FM Suite software interface. The main window is titled 'Project1 - Delft3D FM Suite 2022.04 1D2D (2022.04)'. The 'Flow Data' window is open, showing a table with columns 'Time [yyyy/MM/dd HH:mm:ss]' and 'level [m AD]'. The 'Csv import' button is highlighted with a red box and a circled '4'. The graph area shows a legend for 'level [m AD]' and a plot area with axes for 'Time [yyyy/MM/dd HH:mm:ss]' and 'level [m AD]'. The 'Messages' window at the bottom displays several warnings related to initial conditions and friction data.

Flow Data

Type H(t) : Water level time series

Clipboard import **Csv import** Csv export

Time [yyyy/MM/dd HH:mm:ss]	level [m AD]
	Csv import

00:00:00.000
Time [yyyy/MM/dd HH:mm:ss]

Messages

- While importing initial conditions we encountered the following 2 warnings:
- Could not import channel initial conditions for branch 553, it is not of type Channel. Skipping import of this initial condition. 2023-05-03 20:37:38.123
- Friction data for the following cross-section definitions have not been found. The main bed of branch is used as roughness data. Definition "P01_D75600-0259", cross-section "YS_D75600-0000", branch "YS_504" 2023-05-03 20:37:36.912
- Friction BDFR is linked to branch that does not exist; ignored. 2023-05-03 20:37:36.604
- 470_branch.470

設定上下游邊界條件

匯入下游潮位

Welcome to the wizard

This wizard will allow you to import CSV data

< Previous **Next** > Cancel

Select CSV file

Select the CSV-file containing the data

Filename

Select file

< > << >> << Course > 20230505 > 搜尋 20230505

組合管理 新增資料夾

名稱	修改日期	類型
exercise_01_0505	2023/5/3 下午 08:27	檔案資料夾
rainfall.csv	2023/5/1 下午 11:57	Microsoft Excel...
tide.csv	2023/5/1 下午 11:57	Microsoft Excel...

選擇
tide.csv

檔案名稱(N): tide.csv CSV files (*.csv)

開啟(O) 取消

< Previous Next > Cancel

設定上下游邊界條件

匯入下游潮位

The image shows two side-by-side dialog boxes from a software application. The left dialog, titled "Select CSV file", has a text field containing the file path "C:\WRAP2023\Course\20230505\tide.csv" and a "Next" button highlighted with a red box and the number 9. The right dialog, titled "Parse columns", shows parsing options: "Delimiters" with "Tab" selected, "Use first row as header" checked, and "Ignore empty lines" checked. Below is a "Data preview" table with two columns: "time" and "tide(m)". The table contains data for various times on 2021/7/30 and 2021/7/31. The "Next" button at the bottom right is also highlighted with a red box and the number 10.

Select CSV file
Select the CSV-file containing the data

Filename: C:\WRAP2023\Course\20230505\tide.csv

Parse columns
Please indicate how the data should be parsed into columns

Delimiters:
 Tab Semicolon Use first row as header
 Space Comma Ignore empty lines

Data preview

time	tide(m)
2021/7/30 18:00	0.46
2021/7/30 19:00	0.351
2021/7/30 20:00	0.302
2021/7/30 21:00	0.309
2021/7/30 22:00	0.391
2021/7/30 23:00	0.489
2021/7/31 00:00	0.616
2021/7/31 01:00	0.728
2021/7/31 02:00	0.798

設定上下游邊界條件

匯入下游潮位

Value parsing and column mapping
Please indicate how the values should be parsed and which columns should be used.

Culture info
Date time format:
Number format:

Column selection
Time:
level:

Filtering
 Use filter Filter value:

Input preview

	time	tide(m)
▶	2021/7/30 18:00	0.46
	2021/7/30 19:00	0.351
	2021/7/30 20:00	0.302
	2021/7/30 21:00	0.309
	2021/7/30 22:00	0.391
	2021/7/30 23:00	0.489

Result preview

	Time	level
▶	2021-07-30 18:00:00.000	0.46
	2021-07-30 19:00:00.000	0.351
	2021-07-30 20:00:00.000	0.302
	2021-07-30 21:00:00.000	0.309
	2021-07-30 22:00:00.000	0.391
	2021-07-30 23:00:00.000	0.489
	2021-07-31	0.616

⑪

Finish wizard

Press Finish to close the wizard.

⑫

設定上下游邊界條件

下游潮位匯入完成

The screenshot displays the Delft3D FM Suite interface. The main window shows a 'Flow Data' window with a 'Water level time series' plot. The plot shows water level (level [m AD]) on the y-axis (ranging from 0.3 to 1.0) against time on the x-axis (from 2021-07-31 00:00:00 to 2021-08-01 12:00:00). The plot shows a fluctuating purple line representing the water level. A legend indicates 'level [m AD]'. Below the plot is a table of data points.

Time [yyyy/MM/dd HH:mm:ss]	level [m AD]
2021/07/30 18:00:00	0.46
2021/07/30 19:00:00	0.351
2021/07/30 20:00:00	0.302
2021/07/30 21:00:00	0.309
2021/07/30 22:00:00	0.391
2021/07/30 23:00:00	0.489
2021/07/31 00:00:00	0.616
2021/07/31 01:00:00	0.728
2021/07/31 02:00:00	0.798
2021/07/31 03:00:00	0.811
2021/07/31 04:00:00	0.793
2021/07/31 05:00:00	0.738
2021/07/31 06:00:00	0.675
2021/07/31 07:00:00	0.333
2021/07/31 08:00:00	0.456
2021/07/31 09:00:00	0.458
2021/07/31 10:00:00	0.485
2021/07/31 11:00:00	0.524
2021/07/31 12:00:00	0.605
2021/07/31 13:00:00	0.666
2021/07/31 14:00:00	0.727
2021/07/31 15:00:00	0.765
2021/07/31 16:00:00	0.736
2021/07/31 17:00:00	0.684
2021/07/31 18:00:00	0.616
2021/07/31 19:00:00	0.548
2021/07/31 20:00:00	0.478
2021/07/31 21:00:00	0.444
2021/07/31 22:00:00	0.449
2021/07/31 23:00:00	0.524
2021/08/01 00:00:00	0.662

The Messages window at the bottom shows several warnings:

- While importing initial conditions we encountered the following 2 warnings:
- Could not import channel initial conditions for branch 553, it is not of type Channel. Skipping import of this initial condition.
- Friction data for the following cross-section definitions have not been found. The main bed of branch is used as roughness data. Definition "P01_D75600-0259", cross-section "YS_D75600-0000", branch "YS_504"
- Friction BDFR is linked to branch that does not exist; ignored.
- 470_branch_470

匯入溢堤線

The screenshot shows the Delft3D FM Suite software interface. The main window displays a map with a river and a dam. A context menu is open over the 'Fixed Weirs' layer, with the 'Import...' option selected. A dialog box titled 'Select Type of Data ...' is open, showing 'Features to .pli file' selected. The 'OK' button in the dialog box is highlighted. The messages panel at the bottom shows several warnings related to the import process.

① 右鍵點擊Fixed Weirs

② Import...

③ Features to .pli file

④ OK

Messages

Icon	Message	Time
Warning	While importing initial conditions we encountered the following 2 warnings: Could not import channel initial conditions for branch 553, it is not of type Channel. Skipping import of this initial condition.	2023-05-04 10:58:46.132
Warning	Friction data for the following cross-section definitions have not been found. The main bed of branch is used as roughness data. Definition "P01_D75600-0259", cross-section "YS_D75600-0000", branch "YS_504"	2023-05-04 10:58:44.676
Warning	Friction BDFR is linked to branch that does not exist; ignored. 470_branch.470	2023-05-04 10:58:44.372

匯入溢堤線

Project1 - Delft3D FM Suite 2023.02 1D2D (2023.02)

File Home View Tools Map Spatial Operations Grid

Generate links Add link Embedded 1-to-1 FM Region 1D2D Links

North Arrow Legend Scale Bar

Zoom Previous Zoom Next Query Features Query Time Series

Map Coordinate System Export As Image Show Profile Add dutch layers

Coverage Computational 1D Grid

Network Coverage

Project FM_model

Area Land Boundaries Dry Points Dry Areas Thin Dams Fixed Weirs Levee breaches Observation Point Observation Cros Pumps Weirs Gates Roof Areas Gullies Embankments

Properties

Messages

Time Navigator

Open file

WRAP2023 > vector > 20230505

搜尋 20230505

名稱	修改日期	類型	大小
FlowFM_dike_0.pliz	2023/5/3 上午 08:58	PLIZ 檔案	7,181

選擇 FlowFM_dike_0.pliz

選擇.pliz類型檔案

開啟(O)

取消

Map

- FM_model
 - 1D
 - 2D
 - Area
 - Unstructured Grid
 - Bed Level
 - Initial Water Level
 - Boundary Conditions
 - Boundaries
 - Roughness
 - Viscosity
 - Diffusivity
 - Infiltration
 - Sources and Sinks
 - 1D/2D Links
 - Estimated Grid-snapped
 - Open Street Map

Chart Regi... Map Ope... Tool...

匯入溢堤線

Project1 - Delft3D FM Suite 2023.02 1D2D (2023.02)

Apply coordinate transformation on data?

Import without transformation (as-is)

Transform from: TWD97 / TM2 zone 121

to: TWD97 / TM2 zone 121

OK Cancel

Messages

- While importing initial conditions we encountered the following 2 warnings:
Could not import channel initial conditions for branch 553, it is not of type Channel. Skipping import of this initial condition. 2023-05-04 10:58:46.132
- Friction data for the following cross-section definitions have not been found. The main bed of branch is used as roughness data.
Definition "P01_D75600-0259", cross-section "YS_D75600-0000", branch "YS_504" 2023-05-04 10:58:44.676
- Friction BDFR is linked to branch that does not exist; ignored.
470, branch 470 2023-05-04 10:58:44.372

匯入溢堤線

匯入成功

The screenshot displays the Delft3D FM Suite 2023.02 1D2D (2023.02) software interface. The main window shows a map of a river network with a red area indicating a breach or overflow. The interface includes a menu bar (File, Home, View, Tools, Map, Spatial Operations, Grid), a toolbar with various tools (Generate links, Add link, North Arrow, Legend, Scale Bar, Zoom Previous, Zoom Next, Query Features, Query Time Series, Map Coordinate System, Export As Image, Show Profile, Add dutch layers, Network, Area, Re...), a Project panel on the left showing a tree view of the model (Area, Land Boundaries, Dry Points, Dry Areas, Thin Dams, Fixed Weirs, Levee breaches, Observation Point, Observation Cros, Pumps, Weirs, Gates, Roof Areas, Gullies, Embankments), a Properties panel for the selected network (General: Name network, BranchCount 762, NodeCount 751; Misc: CoordinateSys TWD97 / TM2 zon), and a Messages log at the bottom showing warnings and errors.

Messages log:

Icon	Message	Time
Warning	While importing initial conditions we encountered the following 2 warnings: Could not import channel initial conditions for branch 553, it is not of type Channel. Skipping import of this initial condition.	2023-05-04 10:58:46.132
Error	Friction data for the following cross-section definitions have not been found. The main bed of branch is used as roughness data. Definition "P01_D75600-0259", cross-section "YS_D75600-0000", branch "YS_504"	2023-05-04 10:58:44.676
Error	Friction BDFR is linked to branch that does not exist; ignored. 470 branch 470	2023-05-04 10:58:44.372

匯入建物區塊

① 右鍵點擊Roof Area

② Import...

③ Features to .pol file

④ OK

Messages

Icon	Message	Time
Warning	While importing initial conditions we encountered the following 2 warnings: Could not import channel initial conditions for branch 553, it is not of type Channel. Skipping import of this initial condition.	2023-05-04 10:58:46.132
Error	Friction data for the following cross-section definitions have not been found. The main bed of branch is used as roughness data. Definition "P01_D75600-0259", cross-section "YS_D75600-0000", branch "YS_504"	2023-05-04 10:58:44.676
Error	Friction BDFR is linked to branch that does not exist; ignored. 470_branch.470	2023-05-04 10:58:44.372

匯入建物區塊

Project1 - Delft3D FM Suite 2023.02 1D2D (2023.02)

File Home View Tools Map Spatial Operations Grid

Generate links Add link Embedded 1-to-1 FM Region 1D2D Links Legend Scale Bar North Arrow Zoom Previous Zoom Next Map Coordinate System Export As Image Show Profile Add dutch layers Network Coverage Computational 1D Grid Network Coverage

Project FM_model X

Area Land Boundaries Dry Points Dry Areas Thin Dams Fixed Weirs Levee breaches Observation Point Observation Cros Pumps Weirs Gates Roof Areas Gullies Embankments

Properties

Messages

While importing initial conditions we encountered the following warnings:
Could not import channel initial conditions for branch 553, it is not of type Channel. Skipping import of this initial condition.
Friction data for the following cross-section definitions have not been found. The main bed of branch is used as roughness data.
Definition "P01_D75600-0259", cross-section "YS_D75600-0000", branch "YS_504"
Friction BDFR is linked to branch that does not exist; ignored.
470_branch.470

2023-05-04 10:58:46.132
2023-05-04 10:58:44.676
2023-05-04 10:58:44.372

Chart Regi... Map Ope... Tool...

5 選擇 FlowFM_roofs0.pol

6 開啟(O)

匯入建物區塊

The screenshot displays the Delft3D FM Suite 2023.02 1D2D (2023.02) interface. The main map shows a geographical area with a purple building footprint overlay. A dialog box titled "Apply coordinate transformation on data?" is open, with the "Transform from:" option selected and both "from" and "to" fields set to "TWD97 / TM2-zone 121". The "OK" button is highlighted with a red circle and the number 8. A red circle with the number 7 is also present on the map.

Apply coordinate transformation on data?

- Import without transformation (as-is)
- Transform from: TWD97 / TM2-zone 121
- to: TWD97 / TM2-zone 121
-

Messages

Icon	Message	Time
Warning	While importing initial conditions we encountered the following 2 warnings: Could not import channel initial conditions for branch 553, it is not of type Channel. Skipping import of this initial condition.	2023-05-04 10:58:46.132
Warning	Friction data for the following cross-section definitions have not been found. The main bed of branch is used as roughness data. Definition "P01_D75600-0259", cross-section "YS_D75600-0000", branch "YS_504"	2023-05-04 10:58:44.676
Warning	Friction BDFR is linked to branch that does not exist; ignored. 470_branch.470	2023-05-04 10:58:44.372

匯入建物區塊

The screenshot displays the Delft3D FM Suite 2023.02 1D2D (2023.02) software interface. The main window shows a map of a river network with a yellow grid overlay. The interface includes a menu bar (File, Home, View, Tools, Map, Spatial Operations, Grid), a toolbar with various icons, and a Project panel on the left. The Project panel shows a tree view of the model components, including Area, Land Boundaries, Dry Points, Dry Areas, Thin Dams, Fixed Weirs, Levee breaches, Observation Point, Observation Cros, Pumps, Weirs, Gates, Roof Areas, Gullies, and Embankments. The Properties panel on the left shows the Network properties, including Name (network), BranchCount (762), and NodeCount (751). The Messages panel at the bottom shows several warnings related to initial conditions and friction data.

取消勾選網格，方便等等觀察物件

Map

- FM_model
 - 1D
 - 2D
 - Area
 - Unstructured Grid
 - Bed Level
 - Initial Water Level
 - Boundary Conditions
 - Boundaries
 - Roughness
 - Viscosity
 - Diffusivity
 - Infiltration
 - Sources and Sinks
 - 1D/2D Links
 - Estimated Grid-snapped
 - Open Street Map

匯入建物區塊

匯入成功

The screenshot displays the Delft3D FM Suite 2023.02 1D2D (2023.02) interface. The main map shows a network of channels and structures over a geographic area. A central region is highlighted in pink and labeled "粉紅色區塊" (Pink Area) with a red arrow. The interface includes a top menu bar (File, Home, View, Tools, Map, GIS), a toolbar with various GIS and modeling tools, and a right-hand panel with map settings. The left-hand panel shows a project tree with categories like Area, Land Boundaries, and Pumps. The bottom panel contains a Messages window with the following content:

Icon	Message	Time
Warning	While importing initial conditions we encountered the following 2 warnings: Could not import channel initial conditions for branch 553, it is not of type Channel. Skipping import of this initial condition.	2023-05-04 10:58:46.132
Warning	Friction data for the following cross-section definitions have not been found. The main bed of branch is used as roughness data. Definition "P01_D75600-0259", cross-section "YS_D75600-0000", branch "YS_504"	2023-05-04 10:58:44.676
Warning	Friction BDFR is linked to branch that does not exist; ignored. 470-branch 470	2023-05-04 10:58:44.372

匯入觀測點位

右鍵點擊
Observation Point

1

2

3

4

Messages

Icon	Message	Time
Warning	While importing initial conditions we encountered the following 2 warnings: Could not import channel initial conditions for branch 553, it is not of type Channel. Skipping import of this initial condition.	2023-05-04 10:58:46.132
Error	Friction data for the following cross-section definitions have not been found. The main bed of branch is used as roughness data. Definition "P01_D75600-0259", cross-section "YS_D75600-0000", branch "YS_504"	2023-05-04 10:58:44.676
Error	Friction BDFR is linked to branch that does not exist; ignored. 470, branch 470	2023-05-04 10:58:44.372

匯入觀測點位

The screenshot displays the Delft3D FM Suite 2023.02 1D2D (2023.02) interface. A file explorer window is open, showing the file 'lot_obs_point.xyn' selected in the 'vector > 20230505' folder. The file name is highlighted with a red box and labeled with a circled '5'. Below the file name, the text '選擇 lot_obs_point.xyn' is written in red. The file explorer window has a '開啟(O)' button highlighted with a red box and labeled with a circled '6'. The software interface includes a menu bar (File, Home, View, Tools, Map, Spatial Operations), toolbars (Generate links, Add link, North Arrow, Legend, Scale Bar, Zoom Previous, Zoom Next, Query Features, Query Time Series, Map Coordinate System, Export As Image, Show Profile, Add dutch layers), and a project tree on the left. The map view shows a network of channels with observation points marked. The properties panel on the right shows the 'FM_model' settings, including '1D', '2D', 'Area', 'Boundary Conditions', 'Boundaries', 'Sources and Sinks', and '1D/2D Links'. The 'Messages' panel at the bottom shows warnings about initial conditions and friction data.

匯入觀測點位

匯入成功

The screenshot displays the Delft3D FM Suite 2023.02 1D2D (2023.02) software interface. The main map area shows a street grid with a blue line representing a waterway. A red box highlights a small eye icon on the map, with a white text box overlaid that reads "出現眼睛即為成功" (Appearance of the eye icon indicates success). The software interface includes a menu bar (File, Home, View, Tools, Map), a toolbar with various GIS and map tools, and several panels on the left and right. The left panel shows a project tree with layers like Area, Land Boundaries, and Observation Point. The right panel shows map settings for the FM_model, including 1D and 2D options. The bottom panel shows a Messages window with the following text:

Start importing data 2023-05-04 11:05:16.869
While importing initial conditions we encountered the following 2 warnings:
Could not import channel initial conditions for branch 553, it is not of type Channel. Skipping import of this initial condition. 2023-05-04 10:58:46.132
Friction data for the following cross-section definitions have not been found. The main bed of branch is used as roughness data. 2023-05-04 10:58:44.676
Definition "P01_D75600-0259", cross-section "YS_D75600-0000", branch "YS_504"

流程檢查

遇到驚嘆號的圖示，逐項修正錯誤點

① 右鍵點擊FM_model

② 點擊Validate

③ 確認流程

FM_model (Water Flow FM Model)

- ✓ Sediment Thickness
- ✓ Model Coordinate System
- ✓ Computational grid
- ✓ Network
- ✓ Links
- ✓ Bathymetry
- ✓ Physical Processes
- ✓ Roughness
- ✓ Water flow FM model wind forcing
- ✓ Water flow FM model meteo items
- ✓ WaterFlow FM model definition
- ✓ Water flow FM model boundary conditions
- ✓ Structures
 - ⚠ FixedWeir_2D_00016: fixed weir 'FixedWeir_2D_00016' has unphysical sill depths, parts will be ignored by dflow-fm
 - ⚠ FixedWeir_2D_00047: fixed weir 'FixedWeir_2D_00047' has unphysical sill depths, parts will be ignored by dflow-fm (54 more issues...)
- ✓ Initial Conditions
- ✓ Embankment definitions
- ✓ Enclosure
- ✓ HydroLinks

使用Fixed Weirs替代堤線造成，但模式仍可以模擬

Messages

- Start importing data
- While importing initial conditions we encountered the following 2 warnings:
Could not import channel initial conditions for branch 553, it is not of type Channel. Skipping import of this initial condition.
- Friction data for the following cross-section definitions have not been found. The main bed of branch is used as roughness data.
Definition "P01_D75600-0259", cross-section "YS_D75600-0000", branch "YS_504"

模擬專案 Run Model

關掉 FM_model 的屬性設定視窗，進行儲存後，才能執行專案模擬。

Project1 - Delft3D FM Suite 2023.02 1D2D (2023.02)

Config DIMR

Home Run

Run

FM_model (Water Flow FM Model)

Sediment Thickness

Model Coordinate System

Computational grid

Network

Links

Bathymetry

Physical Processes

Roughness

Water flow FM model wind for

Water flow FM model meteo it

WaterFlow FM model definitio

Water flow FM model boundar

Structures

FixedWeir_2D_00016: fixed w

FixedWeir_2D_00047: fixed w

(54 more issues...)

Initial Conditions

Embankment definitions

Enclosure

HydroLinks

Please wait while processing...

FM_model (Initializing)

Progress: Initializing

耐心等待執行完成

Cancel all activities

Messages

Message	Time
Start importing data	2023-05-04 11:05:16.869
While importing initial conditions we encountered the following 2 warnings: Could not import channel initial conditions for branch 553, it is not of type Channel. Skipping import of this initial condition.	2023-05-04 10:58:46.132
Friction data for the following cross-section definitions have not been found. The main bed of branch is used as roughness data. Definition "P01_D75600-0259", cross-section "YS_D75600-0000", branch "YS_504"	2023-05-04 10:58:44.676

數位簽到資訊 (下午)

本會議採數位簽到，請於以下時間內完成簽到，感謝配合！

簽到時間：2023/05/05 12:00~16:00

*水利署同仁請持公務雲APP簽到

*非水利署同仁（或未安裝公務雲APP之署內同仁），請掃描開啟網頁簽到

<https://cloud.wra.gov.tw/assetBookingCheckIn.do?token=f18a4330ab>

教育訓練目標

- MESH網格建立
- DEM 匯入
- MESH網格高程內插
- 圖資操作
 - 資料匯入、放大、縮小、圖層調整
 - 坐標系統設定
- 水文氣象資料設定與匯入
- 物件新增與刪除
 - 建物區塊、溢堤線、監測點、抽水站、閘門、下水道、河道、斷面
- 模式模擬與檢視

Product name: D-HYDRO vs Delft3D FM

Dutch product name

International product name

- **Product is exactly the same!**

Een decennium D-HYDRO

TKI - D-HYDRO voor waterschappen, deelnemende waterschappen en adviesbureaus

Documentation en validation

above the extent of the 1D computational cells, but this may sometime fully aligning 2D model grids with relatively small 1D channels.

Figure 8.28: Discretization of internal 1D2D links.

Deltares

D-Flow Flexible Mesh, User Manual

Lengths and widths

The distance between the 1D and 2D pressure points for an internal connection is:

$$\Delta x_j = \max(\|x_{R(j)} - x_{L(j)}\|, 0.5\sqrt{ba}) \quad (8.71)$$

where ba represents the area of the 2D grid cell connected to the 1D2D connection.

1D/2D/3D Modelling suite for integral water solutions

Delft3D Flexible Mesh Suite

Deltares Systems

D-Flow FM

82 test cases and 520 pages

Deltares
Enabling Delta Life

Report of all functionality tests

Y	Z	ΔZ storage
0	0	0

profile of 1D channels

[m]	2D Resolution [m]	Embedded Link Type
50	10	1-to-1
10	10	1-to-n
10	10	1-to-1

ern and eastern 1D-2D junctions recorded at the observation c03 and c04, which are shown in Figure 3 to Figure 8. The with the conveyance capacity of the links and are shown in

Figure 3: c02 mass balance at the western 1D to 2D flow junction

Models

1D

- Spatial outline
- Upstream boundary
 - Flow, Qh-relation, Rain
- Downstream boundary
 - Flow, Qh-relation, water level
- Cross-section information
- Initial condition
 - Water level or depth
- Roughness

22-2-2021

2D

- Grid
- Upstream boundary
 - Flow, Qh-relation, Rain
- Downstream boundary
 - Flow, Qh-relation, water level
- DEM
- Initial condition
 - Water level or depth
- Roughness

D-Hydro 1D2D

1D2D

- 1D spatial outline and 2D grid
- Upstream boundary
 - 1D, 2D or both
- Downstream boundary
 - 1D, 2D or both
- Cross-section information
- DEM
- Initial condition
- Roughness

6

輸入輸出設定操作

輸入邊界條件 Boundary Conditions | 雨量輸入 Meteo items | 計算成果輸出 Run model

輸入邊界條件 Boundary Conditions

模擬起迄時間設定 Time Frame | 地理參數 Geometry Parameters

模擬起迄時間設定

The screenshot shows the 'Time Frame' tab in the FlowFM software. The settings are as follows:

Parameter	Value
Max Courant nr	0.7
Reference date	23/Aug/2018 00:00:00
Time zone	0
User time step	0d 01: 00: 00.000
Max. time step (s)	3600
Initial time step (s)	3600
Update interval for time dep roughness (s)	86400
Start Time	23/Aug/2018 00:00:00
Stop Time	25/Aug/2018 23:00:00

地理單位設定
長度、最小單位、寬度

The screenshot shows the 'Physical Parameters' tab in the FlowFM software. The settings are as follows:

Parameter	Value
Default 1D channel width	2
Conveyance-2D type	R=HU
Nonlinear iteration 2D	No
Non-linear 1D volumes	Preissmann slot
Extend 1D end nodes?	<input type="checkbox"/>
Preissmann slot width 2D	0
Preissmann slot width 1D	0.005
Minimum 1D edge length	1
Allow 1d boundary at endnode when connecting branch leads to bifurcation	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Use Volume Tables	<input type="checkbox"/>

輸入雨量資料

專案管理欄 FM_model > 2D > Physical Parameters > Meteo items

點選 add 新增雨量資料

輸入雨量資料

點選 csv 檔案並 匯入 | 匯入資料以後，即可在軟體介面上瀏覽雨量資料

雨量參數調整

起始條件 Initial Conditions | 物理參數 Physical Parameters

The screenshot shows the 'Initial Conditions' tab in the FlowFM software. It is divided into two sections: 'Initial conditions (1D)' and 'Initial conditions (2D)'. In the 1D section, 'Quantity' is set to 'Water depth' and 'Value' is '0.1'. In the 2D section, 'Quantity' is set to 'Water level' and 'Value' is '0'. A 'Restart file' field is also present but empty.

起始條件：水深、水位設定

The screenshot shows the 'Physical Parameters' tab in the FlowFM software. It is divided into three sections: 'Bed level', 'Roughness (2D)', and 'Roughness (1D)'. In the 'Bed level' section, 'Uniform bed level' is '-5', 'Bed slope' is '0', and 'Bed level locations' is 'faces (cell centers)'. In the 'Roughness (2D)' section, 'Uniform friction coefficient' is '0.023' and 'Uniform friction type' is 'Manning'. In the 'Roughness (1D)' section, 'Uniform friction coefficient' is '0.023' and 'Uniform friction type' is 'Manning'. The 'Others' section shows 'Gravity' set to '9.81'.

物理參數：糙度係數設定

數值參數 Numerical Parameters

數值參數 Numerical Parameters | 固定堰參數 Fixed Weir Parameters

The screenshot displays the 'FlowFM (FM model settings)' window with the 'Numerical Parameters' tab selected. The interface is divided into two main sections: 'Numerical Parameters' and 'Fixed weir parameters'.

Numerical Parameters:

- Advection type: Perot q(ui-o-u) fast
- Position of z boundary: Delft3D-FLOW
- Boundary smoothing time: 0
- Turbulence advection: horizontally explicit and vertically implicit
- Water level threshold: 0
- Velocity threshold: 0
- Dry cell threshold: 0.0001
- Stop criterium non linear: 0.0001
- Stop criterium Nested Newton: 0.0001
- Max non linear iterations: 100
- Usage of Pure 1D solver: 0
- Check positive waterdepth: 1.0*dts (close all links)
- Include user Qin/out:

Fixed weir parameters:

- Fixed weir scheme: Numerical
- Fixed weir contraction: 1
- Fixed weir friction scheme: Subgrid Weir
- Fixed weir top width: 3
- Fixed weir top friction: -999
- Fixed weir talud: 4

Urban:

- Apply drop losses:
- Horizontal Bobs 1d2d:

設定邊界條件

氣象資料 | 上下游邊界條件 | 側入流 | 抽水機

氣象資料

- ✓ 在介面中如果沒有使用 RR 模組，則單一降雨量設定單位為mm/day
- ✓ 批次模擬專案內容，可以使用網格降雨量

上下游 邊界條件

流量 | 水位 | 潮位

側入流

流量 | 水位

抽水機

抽水量 | 起抽水位 |
停抽水位

設定上下游邊界

The screenshot displays the Delft3D FM Suite 2022.02.102D (2022.02) software interface. The top menu bar includes File, Home, View, Tools, and Map. The Home tab is active, showing options like 'Generate links', 'North Arrow', 'Legend', and 'Scale Bar'. The 'Map' tab is also visible. The main workspace shows a map with a vertical line segment representing a boundary. A dialog box titled 'Boundary01 (Boundary conditions) X' is open, showing 'Location' and 'Geometry' fields. The 'Geometry' field contains a vertical line segment. Below the dialog, there are buttons for 'Import from files...', 'Export to files...', and 'Combined BC view'. The left sidebar shows a tree view of the project structure, including '2D', 'Area', 'Land Boundaries', 'Dry Points', 'Dry Areas', 'Thin Dams', 'Fixed Weirs', 'Levee breaches', 'Observation Points', 'Observation Cross-Sections', 'Pumps', 'Weirs', 'Sates', 'Roof Areas', 'Gullies', 'Embankments', 'Enclosure', 'Bridge Pillars', 'Grid', 'Sed Level', 'Initial Conditions', 'Initial Water Level', 'Boundary Conditions', 'Boundary01', 'Boundary02', 'Physical Parameters', 'Physical Parameters', 'Viscosity', 'Diffusivity', 'Infiltration', 'Meteo items', 'Wind', 'Sources and Sinks', '1D2D Links', and 'Output'. The 'Boundary Conditions' folder is expanded, showing 'Boundary01' and 'Boundary02'. A text box with a red arrow points to the 'Boundary01' folder in the tree view.

1. 點選新增2D邊界條件

2. 圖面上選擇位置點或匯入線段資訊

3. 點選設定2D邊界條件

設定上下游邊界

Boundary Condition

Flow

- Water level
- Water level
- Velocity
- Riemann invariant
- Neumann gradient
- Discharge

Location

Geometry

4. 選擇邊界條件型態

水位
流速
流量

設定側入流

點選新增2D邊界 | 條件圖面上選擇位置點 | 點選設定側入流數值

圖示	名稱	說明	手冊章節
	一般堰壩	可自行調整壩頂水位、壩頂寬度等	Ch.5.4.2.9
	閘門	可選擇所需閘門屬性，並進行屬性編輯	Ch.5.4.2.10
	堤防潰壩	現場若有堤防潰壩，可繪製此物件作為表達	
	陸地邊界	水和陸地的交界點	Ch.5.4.2.6
	乾燥點	不會淹水的地方，以點型態呈現，一般適用於墩柱	Ch.5.4.2.7
	乾燥區	不會淹水的地方，以區域型態呈現，一般適用於建築物、構造物	Ch.5.4.2.7
	建物區塊	建物區塊範圍可搭配雨水下水道系統	
	橋樑	可設定橋樑類型與詳細設定	Ch.5.4.2.11

圖示	名稱	說明	手冊章節
	薄壩	可讓兩個網格間有設定一個薄牆，讓網格和網格之間水體不會交換，水也不會溢過薄壩	Ch.5.4.2.4
	固定堰壩	功能與薄壩相同，但是可調整或固定堰壩高程數值	Ch.5.4.2.5
	觀測點	可設定該點的觀測水位，以及流速、溫度等各式資料(可做為重要檢核點)	Ch.5.4.2.2
	斷面觀測	可觀測各類資料剖資料檢視	Ch.5.4.2.3
	抽水機	可進行抽水量設定	Ch.5.4.2.8

溝渠

堤防

局部區域模擬

新增二維物件(建物區塊)

1	DryArea00000	CRIF			
2	3	2	CRIF		
3	170327.5522	2549589.1841	CRIF		
4	170613.9177	2549438.6917	CRIF		
5	170527.9221	2549281.3197	CRIF		
6	DryArea00001	CRIF			
7	3	2	CRIF		
8	170394.6288	2549719.8976	CRIF		
9	170613.0578	2549604.6634	CRIF		
10	170598.4385	2549452.451	CRIF		
11	DryArea00002	CRIF			
12	3	2	CRIF		
13	170517.6026	2549940.9064	CRIF		
14	170789.3489	2549798.1536	CRIF		
15	170782.4692	2549722.4774	CRIF		
16	DryArea00003	CRIF			
17	8	2	CRIF		
18	170504.7032	2549849.751	CRIF		
19	170774.7296	2549712.158	CRIF		
20	170721.4123	2549601.2235	CRIF		
21	170621.6573	2549640.7815	CRIF		
22	170627.677	2549698.3986	CRIF		
23	170589.8389	2549720.7575	CRIF		
24	170555.4407	2549651.101	CRIF		
25	170445.3662	2549713.8779	CRIF		
26	DryArea00004	CRIF			
27	3	2	CRIF		
28	170641.4363	2550150.7359	CRIF		
29	170730.7866	2550104.2058	CRIF		
30	170748.071	2550015.7227	CRIF		
31	DryArea00005	CRIF			
32	3	2	CRIF		
33	170595.8586	2550080.2194	CRIF		
34	170751.5108	2550006.2631	CRIF		
35	170775.5896	2549918.5476	CRIF		

新增二維物件(建物區塊)

- 使用 roof area

新增二維物件(建物區塊)

- 使用dry area

roof area vs dry area

新增二維物件(溢堤線)

1	FixedWeir_2D_00000	CRIF				
2	...72...5	CRIF				
3	181949.6318	2539155.0479	36.7879	36.7879	36.7879	CRIF
4	181948.283	2539154.795	36.873	36.873	36.873	CRIF
5	181944.453	2539154.052	37.039	37.039	37.039	CRIF
6	181935.831	2539150.967	36.713	36.713	36.713	CRIF
7	181931.499	2539149.837	36.642	36.642	36.642	CRIF
8	181925.901	2539148.791	36.708	36.708	36.708	CRIF
9	181922.368	2539148.186	37.168	37.168	37.168	CRIF
10	181918.8245	2539148.1985	36.8445	36.8445	36.8445	CRIF
11	181915.281	2539148.211	36.521	36.521	36.521	CRIF
12	181903.447	2539146.293	36.245	36.245	36.245	CRIF
13	181901.5207	2539145.501	35.9462	35.9462	35.9462	CRIF
14	181899.5945	2539144.709	35.6475	35.6475	35.6475	CRIF
15	181897.6682	2539143.917	35.3487	35.3487	35.3487	CRIF
16	181895.742	2539143.125	35.05	35.05	35.05	CRIF
17	181893.8158	2539142.333	34.7512	34.7512	34.7512	CRIF
18	181891.8895	2539141.541	34.4525	34.4525	34.4525	CRIF
19	181889.9633	2539140.749	34.1537	34.1537	34.1537	CRIF
20	181888.037	2539139.957	33.855	33.855	33.855	CRIF
21	181884.415	2539139.736	33.801	33.801	33.801	CRIF
22	181878.98	2539137.86	33.369	33.369	33.369	CRIF
23	181869.976	2539130.466	33.517	33.517	33.517	CRIF
24	181877.143	2539120.513	34.004	34.004	34.004	CRIF
25	181884.9	2539110.937	33.791	33.791	33.791	CRIF
26	181888.954	2539105.755	34.041	34.041	34.041	CRIF
27	181891.205	2539103.837	34.073	34.073	34.073	CRIF
28	181896.339	2539098.119	34.438	34.438	34.438	CRIF
29	181901.473	2539092.401	34.803	34.803	34.803	CRIF
30	181909.375	2539084.083	35.02	35.02	35.02	CRIF
31	181909.4037	2539084.06	35.0202	35.0202	35.0202	CRIF
32	181904.112	2539075.2447	34.2707	34.2707	34.2707	CRIF
33	181891.758	2539086.432	34.418	34.418	34.418	CRIF
34	181881.343	2539097.988	34.002	34.002	34.002	CRIF
35	181873.145	2539107.476	33.512	33.512	33.512	CRIF
36	181867.753	2539114.592	33.53	33.53	33.53	CRIF
37	181866.233	2539116.587	33.8345	33.8345	33.8345	CRIF

新增二維物件(監測點位) 淹水感測器

1	170121	2553409	RM006_240	CRIF
2	169297	2553875	RM006_242	CRIF
3	165699	2551998	RM006_243	CRIF
4	168186	2553048	RM006_245	CRIF
5	167866	2553056	RM006_246	CRIF
6	165468	2550331	RM006_247	CRIF
7	167827	2550651	RM006_248	CRIF
8	165451	2550709	RM006_249	CRIF
9	166976	2549270	RM006_250	CRIF
10	168464	2548779	RM006_251	CRIF
11	168319	2548803	RM006_252	CRIF
12	167345	2549410	RM006_253	CRIF
13	167990	2548995	RM006_254	CRIF
14	167313	2549813	RM006_255	CRIF
15	164021	2550444	RM006_256	CRIF
16	164998	2550246	RM006_257	CRIF
17	166755	2549211	RM006_258	CRIF
18	167964	2553211	RM006_260	CRIF
19	165725	2549904	RM006_261	CRIF
20	168756	2548945	RM006_263	CRIF
21	169170	2548382	RM006_264	CRIF
22	166907	2550932	RM006_265	CRIF
23	165889	2551592	RM006_267	CRIF
24	165912	2551426	RM006_268	CRIF
25	165818	2552276	RM006_269	CRIF
26	168600	2548941	RM006_270	CRIF
27	166391	2548987	RM006_271	CRIF
28	169202	2549272	RM006_272	CRIF
29				

新增二維物件 (閘門)

點選圖示後可以直接繪製 | 對著閘門點兩下，即可設定數值

新增二維物件 (堰壩)

點選圖示後可以直接繪製 | 對著堰壩點兩下，即可設定數值

新增二維物件 (抽水機)

點選圖示後可以直接繪製 | 對著抽水機點兩下，即可設定抽水量

二維物件 (抽水機) 進階設定

設定時需要考慮方向性

Pumps X

Show only map selection

Name	Long name	Branch	Positive direction	Capacity	Start delivery	Stop delivery	Start suction	Stop suction	Control on	Group name
Pump_2D_01			<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	1	0	0	3	2	Suction side	

Suction side
Delivery side
Suction and delivery side

抽水機控制方式

- 抽水
- 排水
- 抽水排水

Pump properties

Capacity m³/s (= 60 m³/min, 3600 m³/h)

Positive Negative

Y Offset

Pump control levels

Switch-on level: Switch-off level:

Suction side : m m

Delivery side : m m

Reduction table

抽水機控制水位

- 堤內 | 起抽水水位 | 停抽水水位
- 堤外 | 排水水位 | 停止水位

可以透過QGIS對 增加抽水站圖層進行檢查

No.	District	Pump stati	Pump type	Pump diame	Total pump	Pump quant	Pumpage(CM)
1	永康區	永康分洪抽水站	豎軸式	1350	32.0000000000000000	8	4.0*8
2	永康區	三坎店抽水站	豎軸式	1350	12.0000000000000000	3	4.0*3
3	永康區	永康抽水站	豎軸式	2000	40.0000000000000000	5	8.0*5
4	永康區	永康異抽水站	豎軸式	1800	25.5000000000000000	3	8.5*3
5	安南區	和順寮抽水站	豎軸式	1000	4.0000000000000000	2	2.0*2
6	安定區	安定抽水站	豎軸式	1100	10.0000000000000000	4	2.5*4
7	安南區	九份子抽水站	豎軸式 沉水式	1350 700	12.0000000000000000	6	4.0*2 1.0*4
8	北區	文賢抽水站	豎軸式	1350	16.0000000000000000	4	4.0*4
9	北區	北安抽水站	豎軸式	1850	32.0000000000000000	4	8.0*4
10	安平區	安平抽水站	沉水式	500	15.1999999999999999	8	3.0*2 1.0*4
11	南區	鯉鯉抽水站	沉水式	1200	8.0000000000000000	4	2.0*4
12	南區	喜樹抽水站	豎軸式	1500	25.0000000000000000	5	5.0*5
13	南區	海裡抽水站	豎軸式	1650	19.8000000000000001	3	6.6*3
14	安南區	本湖寮A抽水站	豎軸式	1200	7.0000000000000000	2	3.5*2
15	安南區	天馬抽水站	豎軸式	1100	5.0000000000000000	2	2.5*2

SOBEK專案匯入

- 建議使用2.15 2.16版本
- 斷面資料檢查 2.13前版本需要
- 抽水機需要調整
- 避免中文字串
- 小區塊分區測試匯入

SOBEK專案匯入

使用SOEBK 專案 TN_YS1.lit

SOBEK WaterFlow FM importer

Select SOBEK case or network file

Filename: C:\WRAP2023\Course\20230505\exercise_01_0505\TN_YS1 lit\TN_YS1 lit\CASELIST.CMT

Select a case:

- 3 for Delft3d1d2d

< Previous **Next >** Cancel

Messages

- Updated spatial operations of coverage Bed Level with changed grid. 2023-05-03 20:35:45.619
- Running this model requires the OutputDirectory to be overwritten to: output 2023-05-03 20:33:13.515
- Project Project1 saved 2023-05-03 20:33:13.290
- Creating database session ... 2023-05-03 20:33:12.790
- Creating database schema ... 2023-05-03 20:33:12.749

調整計算節點

Remove computational grid nodes

The screenshot displays the Delft3D FM Suite 2022.04 1D2D (2022.04) interface. The main map shows a river network with a dense grid of blue and red nodes. A right-click context menu is open over the grid, with the option "Remove computational grid nodes" highlighted in red. A red circle with the number "3" is placed over the right-click action, and another red circle with the number "4" is placed over the highlighted menu option. The "Messages" panel at the bottom left shows several warning messages, with the second message highlighted in red. The "Map" panel on the right shows the "FM_model" layer selected, with "1D" and "2D" sub-layers checked. The "1D/2D Links" sub-layer is also checked. The "Open Street Map" option is checked at the bottom of the "Map" panel.

Project1 - Delft3D FM Suite 2022.04 1D2D (2022.04)

File Home View Tools Map GIS Spatial Operations Grid Config DIMR

Generate links Add link Embedded 1-to-1 FM Region 1D2D Links

North Arrow Legend Scale Bar

Spatial Operations: Zoom Previous, Zoom Next, Query Features, Map Coordinate System, Export As Image, Query Time Series

Tools: Edit, Grid Profile, Background, Network, Area, Region

Map: Add Route, Show Side View, Coverage, Network Coverage

Project: FM_model

- General
- 1D
- 2D
- Area
- Grid
- Bed Level
- Initial Conditions
- Boundary Condition
- Physical Parameters
- Sources and Sinks
- 1D2D Links
- Output

Map: Use focused layer

- FM_model
- 1D
- 2D
- Area
- Unstructured Grid
- Bed Level
- Initial Water Level
- Boundary Conditions
- Boundaries
- Roughness
- Viscosity
- Diffusivity
- Infiltration
- Sources and Sinks
- 1D/2D Links
- Estimated Grid-snapped
- Open Street Map

Messages

- While importing initial conditions we encountered the following 2 warnings:
- Could not import channel initial conditions for branch 553, it is not of type Channel. Skipping import of this initial condition.
- Friction data for the following cross-section definitions have not been found. The main bed of branch is used as roughness data. Definition "P01_D75600-0259", cross-section "YS_D75600-0000", branch "YS_504"
- Friction BDFR is linked to branch that does not exist; ignored.
- 470_branch.470

Remove computational grid nodes

2023-05-03 20:37:36.912

2023-05-03 20:37:36.604

調整計算節點

Generate computational grid nodes in selected branch(es)

The screenshot displays the Delft3D FM Suite 2022.04 1D2D (2022.04) interface. The main map shows a river network with a dense cluster of blue dots representing computational grid nodes. A red circle labeled '3' highlights a specific node, with the text '點擊右鍵' (Click right button) next to it. A context menu is open over this node, and a red circle labeled '4' highlights the option 'Generate computational grid nodes in selected branch(es)'. To the right of the menu, the text '新增計算節點' (Add computational nodes) is written in red. The interface includes a top menu bar (File, Home, View, Tools, Map, GIS, Config, DIMR), a toolbar with various GIS and network tools, and a left-hand project tree. The project tree shows a hierarchy for 'Project1' > 'FM_model' > 'Grid'. The right-hand side features a 'Map' panel with layer visibility options for 'FM_model', '1D', '2D', 'Area', 'Bed Level', 'Initial Water Level', 'Boundary Conditions', 'Boundaries', 'Roughness', 'Viscosity', 'Infiltration', 'Sources and Sinks', '1D/2D Links', 'Estimated Grid-snapped', and 'Open Street Map'. A 'Messages' panel at the bottom left shows several warning messages related to initial conditions and friction data. A 'Time Navigator' panel is visible at the bottom right.

調整計算節點

⑤ 選擇框選選項

⑥

⑦ 填入 50 m

Generate Computational Grid

Create segments for:

- All branches
- Selected branches

If branch already has grid points:

- Generate new grid points
- Use existing grid points

Positions:

- None (Remove grid from branch)
- Preferred length: 50 m

Special locations:

- Cross Section
- Lateral Sources
- Structure: 10 m in front and behind
- Minimum cell length: 0.5 m

Messages

- While importing initial conditions we encountered the following 2 warnings:
- Could not import channel initial conditions for branch 553, it is not of type Channel. Skipping import of this initial condition. 2023-05-03 20:37:38.123
- Friction data for the following cross-section definitions have not been found. The main bed of branch is used as roughness data. Definition "P01_D75600-0259", cross-section "YS_D75600-0000", branch "YS_504" 2023-05-03 20:37:36.912
- Friction BDFR is linked to branch that does not exist; ignored. 2023-05-03 20:37:36.604
- 470_branch.470

建立1D2D連結

使用 **Generate links**

① **Generate links**

② 將網格和SOBEK物件一起框選(左鍵兩下可自動連接回起始點)

Project1 - Delft3D FM Suite 2022.04 1D2D (2022.04)

File View Tools Map GIS Config
Spatial Operations Grid DIMR
Map Coordinate System Show Profile Add ditch layers
Zoom Previous Zoom Next Export As Image Query Features Query Time Series
FM Region 1D2D Links Decorations Edit Grid Profile Backgrou... Network Area Region Network Coverage
Add Route Show Side View
Embedded 1-to-1 Legend Scale Bar

Project1
FM_model
General
1D
2D
Area
Grid
Bed Level
Initial Conditions
Boundary Condition
Physical Parameters
Sources and Sinks
1D2D Links
Output

Map
Use focused layer
FM_model
1D
2D
Area
Unstructured Grid
Bed Level
Initial Water Level
Boundary Conditions
Boundaries
Roughness
Viscosity
Diffusivity
Infiltration
Sources and Sinks
1D/2D Links
Estimated Grid-snapped
Open Street Map
temp_layer

Messages
While importing initial conditions we encountered the following 2 warnings:
Could not import channel initial conditions for branch 553, it is not of type Channel. Skipping import of this initial condition.
Friction data for the following cross-section definitions have not been found. The main bed of branch is used as roughness data.
Definition "P01_D75600-0259", cross-section "YS_D75600-0000", branch "YS_504"
Friction BDFR is linked to branch that does not exist; ignored.
470_branch.470

2023-05-03 20:37:38.123
2023-05-03 20:37:36.912
2023-05-03 20:37:36.604

Chart Regi... Map Ope... Tool...

HyDEM規格

產品名稱

水利數值地形資料集產品說明

水利數值地形分類點雲
HyDEM LAS

將內政部空載光達案成果補正水利結構物 (如：溝渠兩側立面、防洪牆、胸牆、各式堤防等)

水利數值地形模型
HyDEM

空載光達之地面點及三維水利圖徵之溢堤線、海陸線、海堤線所內插而得的1公尺網格

三維水利圖徵
3D Hydraulic Feature

包含建物區塊(資料表)、溢堤線、水域區塊、海陸線、海堤線共計五種類別

三維水利圖徵

